

Some Recent Studies in Surface Reactivity of Microcrystalline Carbons

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The present review covers recent research in the field of surface reactivity of microcrystalline carbons with particular reference to the nature of the sites and mechanisms involved in chemisorption of oxygen, chlorine, bromine, iodine and sulphur on various treatments. The role of certain highly reactive sites, referred to as unsaturated sites, in chemisorption of the various species and in catalysing a number of reactions, as revealed in recent research, has been highlighted. The recent trends to spell out the effect of each oxygen complex separately in altering surface characteristics, such as hydrophilicity, polarity and selectivity in adsorption from binary solutions of non-electrolytes, have been pointed out and the results obtained so far have been discussed.

CARBON is regarded as a unique element for several good reasons. One such reason, though not always realised, is its remarkable property of chemisorbing other elements, notably oxygen, hydrogen, nitrogen, the halogens and sulphur, giving rise to stable surface compounds, usually called surface complexes. It is now known that in carbons, the fraction which exists in the form of disordered single stacked layers is more susceptible while the fraction which shows some degree of well-ordered parallel stacking is less susceptible to chemisorption of various species. The disordered fraction is higher in microcrystalline carbons than in crystalline carbons. At the same time there are many exposed defects, dislocations and discontinuities in the layer planes of microcrystalline carbons, apart from the edges of the carbon layers. Such sites, called the "active sites" are associated with high concentrations of unpaired electron spin centre and, therefore, play a significant role in chemisorption. A considerable amount of literature, dealing with the formation, stability, structure and properties of the various surface complexes on carbons, has been made available during the past two decades, as has been discussed elsewhere by the author (1).

The more recent trends of research in this field during the last 5 or 6 years, covered by this review, have been towards understanding the specific sites involved in chemical fixation of the various species, the role of some of these sites in catalytic reactions of carbons, and the influence of the chemisorbed species on surface behaviour of carbons. The identification of certain highly reactive sites, referred to as unsaturated sites, which are generated on heat

treatment of carbons in vacuum at a temperature close to 700°, and their estimation by reacting carbons with aqueous bromine, reported in earlier publications from these laboratories (2,3), have proved to be highly useful. Some further investigations (4,5,6) have shown that these sites constitute a definite and reproducible quantity at a given stage in the history of formation of a carbon and can be enhanced within limits on treatment of the carbon with a mild oxidising solution, like aqueous potassium persulphate, followed by evacuation at 700°. A few of the data are presented in Table I with a view to illustrate the type of results obtained. Thus, a convenient method for preparing carbons with a high degree of chemical reactivity is now available. Treatment of carbons in aqueous suspension with ozonised oxygen, followed by evacuation at 700°, has also been used as an alternative method (7) for the same purpose.

TABLE I. ESTIMATION OF UNSATURATED SITES IN CARBONS IN TERMS OF IRREVERSIBLE FIXATION OF BROMINE

Sample	Bromine fixed irreversibly (milligram atom/g.)
(1)	(2)
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>	
A	378
B	514
<i>Coconut shell charcoal</i>	
A	354
B	455
<i>Mogul</i>	
A	61
B	151
<i>ELF-O</i>	
A	39
B	91

A—outgassed as such at 700°.

B—outgassed at 700° after oxidation with aqueous $K_2S_2O_8$

The chemisorption kinetics of oxygen on Graphon, a highly graphitised carbon black, at 25°C under oxygen pressure range of 0.7 millitorr to 760 torr (8) and also at a constant pressure of 100 millitorr in the temperature range of -78 to 160°(9) have been investigated by Walker and coworkers. By applying Elovich equation to their results, these workers have shown that the plots of the amount of oxygen chemisorbed versus log of time give five different linear regions which, according to them, indicate the presence of five different types of reactive sites involved in the process. They have speculated with regard to the nature of such sites, on the basis of carbon-carbon distances in the same as well as adjacent layer planes, but there has been no evidence so far to support this point of view. However, by using oxygen at pressure of one atmosphere at 25° (9) or at a low pressure of 100 millitorr at 350° (10), they could detect the presence of only two main types of active sites referred to as type I & type II sites; the type I sites being far more reactive than the type II sites. Our work on chemisorption kinetics of oxygen at 200°, 300° and 350° by sugar charcoal, before and after activation in oxygen at 650° to 38 per cent weight loss, under oxygen pressure of one atmosphere (11), while supporting the observations of Walker and coworkers, has shown that the more energetic sites corresponding to type I are, in fact, the unsaturated sites referred to in the above paragraph. The oxygen chemisorbed at these sites has been shown to come off as carbon dioxide on high-temperature evacuation, but unlike such oxygen in most other cases (12, 13), it does not impart acidity to the carbon surface. If the unsaturated sites are blocked, partially or completely, by bromine, the extent of chemisorption of oxygen at these sites falls correspondingly.

The oxygen chemisorbed at type II sites has been shown to come off as carbon monoxide and nearly half of this appears to be quinonic oxygen, as indicated from the uptake of hydrogen on reacting with sodium borohydride. These sites appear to be constituted by the edge carbon atoms in the basal planes (14).

Chemisorption of oxygen also occurs at certain additional active centres, constituted partially by defects and dislocations in the layer planes, if the gas is led over a rotating bed of a carbon heated to 400° (15) which is known to be optimum temperature for maximum fixation of the gas. This oxygen comes off as carbon dioxide but, unlike that chemisorbed at the unsaturated sites, imparts an equivalent amount of surface acidity (12, 13) and is, therefore, referred to as the acidic CO_2^- complex. This complex is also

formed on treatment of carbons with oxidising solutions such as aqueous potassium persulphate and hydrogen peroxide (13, 15).

Interaction of carbons with the halogens, other than fluorine, has also been investigated by several workers during the past few years. The optimum temperature for maximum chemisorption has been found to be 400° for chlorine (16, 17), 500° for bromine (18) and 300° for iodine. The reaction, in each case, also involves appreciable dehydrogenation of the carbon resulting in formation of the hydrogen halide. The chemisorption, in each case, has been found (20) to involve addition at the unsaturated sites and substitution of hydrogen associated with the edge carbon atoms. Since unsaturated sites are rather few in carbon blacks, the major portion of the halogen is fixed by substitution process. In charcoals and activated carbons, the hydrogen content is low but unsaturated sites are high, hence bulk of the fixation takes place by the addition process. The relative amounts of fixation of the halogens, under respective optimum conditions, decrease in the order $\text{Cl}_2 > \text{Br}_2 > \text{I}_2$ (21). The stability of the surface complexes also decreases in the same order (19, 21).

A study of simultaneous chemisorption of oxygen and chlorine at 400° shows that while both the gases compete with each other for fixation at the unsaturated sites, there are other separate sites where fixation of oxygen and chlorine can take place independently of each other (22). These sites, for the fixation of oxygen, are provided by certain active centres where formation of acidic CO_2^- complex and quinonic or phenolic groups is possible and for the fixation of chlorine by edge carbon atoms associated with hydrogen. Oxygen has been found to be more rapidly chemisorbed at the unsaturated sites than chlorine under similar conditions. Simultaneous chemisorption of oxygen and chlorine on treatment of carbons with chlorine water (23) or with H_2O_2 -HCl mixture (24) with, more or less, similar conclusions have also been reported.

Chemisorption of sulphur by carbons on suitable treatment has also been investigated by different workers in recent years. Thus, treatment of carbon blacks with aqueous hydrogen sulphide at room temperature has been shown to result in appreciable fixation of sulphur almost exclusively at the unsaturated sites (25), as shown by the data given in Table II. The amount of sulphur fixed is seen to be almost equivalent to surface unsaturation present initially in the carbon black (i.e., one sulphur atom = two

bromine atoms). If there is no surface unsaturation in a carbon black, there is no fixation of sulphur.

is well known (31), can be catalysed by combined sulphur, organic or inorganic, soluble or insoluble, but not at all by free sulphur.

TABLE II. AMOUNTS OF SULPHUR FIXED BY CARBON BLACKS IN RELATION TO SURFACE UNSATURATION

Sample	Sulphur fixed (milligram atom/100g.)	Surface unsaturation (milligram atom/100g.)	
		Before fixation of sulphur	After fixation of sulphur
<i>Mogul</i>			
A	nil	nil	nil
B	40	72	nil
<i>Mogul-A</i>			
A	nil	nil	nil
B	35	64	nil
<i>ELF-O</i>			
A	nil	nil	nil
B	21	39	nil
<i>Spheron-4</i>			
A	25	45	nil
B	31	64	nil

A—Original sample

B—700° outgassed sample

Treatments with sulphur, carbon disulphide and hydrogen sulphide at elevated temperatures, however, result in additional fixation of sulphur at certain other sites as well (25-28). The optimum temperature for maximum fixation has been found to be around 600° in each case. There appear to be three distinct categories of mechanisms and sites which, between themselves, can account for the total chemisorption of sulphur. These are: (i) addition at the unsaturated sites as in the case of treatment with aqueous hydrogen sulphide, (ii) fixation at certain active centres on the surface forming stable C=S covalent bonds, and (iii) substitution of the oxygen of phenolic and quinonic groups initially present on the carbon surface yielding thiophenolic and thioquinonic structures. The view of some of the workers (29) that the sulphur fixed by carbons may not be held truly chemically but may be entrapped as a polymer in the micropore structure has not been substantiated. A considerable evidence for chemical fixation has been adduced from the observation that carbon blacks which, ordinarily, do not catalyse the sodium azide-iodine reaction, do so appreciably after fixation of sulphur (25, 30). This reaction, as

The carbon-sulphur surface complexes have been found to be highly stable (25, 26). The desorption of the combined sulphur commences on evacuating at temperatures > 600°, largely as hydrogen sulphide and carbon disulphide and is completed only at 1000°. This establishes a close analogy between carbon-sulphur and carbon-oxygen surface complexes since the combined oxygen is known to come off as water vapour and oxides of carbon under similar conditions (1).

Catalytic reactions of carbons

A few investigations on some important catalytic reactions of carbons, associated with unsaturated sites referred to occasionally in the previous pages, have also been made in recent years. It has been found, for example, that the conversion of bromine into hydrogen bromide in a current of hydrogen which, ordinarily, does not take place at all even upto 300°,¹ proceeds to near completion even at 150° in the presence of carbons having unsaturated sites (32). The activation energy of the reaction which, ordinarily, under similar experimental conditions is of the order of 50 kcal/mole falls to about 10 kcal/mole in the presence of the carbon.

Similarly, the conversion of iodine into hydrogen iodide in a current of hydrogen, which is a highly activated process, takes place to nearly 90 per cent completion at 300° in the presence of the carbon having unsaturated sites (33). The activation energy of the reaction falls to about 12 kcal/mole. The catalytic efficiency of a carbon, for both the reactions mentioned above, depends not on the magnitude of surface area but on the presence of unsaturated sites. If these sites are pre-occupied with oxygen or sulphur, the catalytic effect almost disappears. The mechanism proposed is that bromine (or iodine, as the case may be) is adsorbed dissociatively at the unsaturated sites and the hydrogen then reacts with the resulting surface complex removing bromine (or iodine) atoms as hydrogen bromide (or hydrogen iodide). The carbon itself does not undergo any change and can be used over and over again.

The unsaturated sites have been found to be involved also in catalytic oxidation of hydrogen sulphide in oxygen to give sulphur(34). The reaction takes place appreciably even at 120°, proceeds

towards 90 per cent completion at 180° and near completion at 220°. An appreciable amount of sulphur is chemisorbed at the unsaturated sites.

Interaction with sulphur dioxide has been found (35, 36) to take place appreciably at temperatures > 300°, involving chemical fixation of sulphur by the carbon, and formation of free sulphur, sulphuric acid and hydrogen sulphide. At 600°, almost the entire amount of sulphur dioxide mixed with nitrogen in the ratio of 1 : 3, 1 : 7 or 1 : 15 passed over 5 g. charcoal bed @ 21./hr for 2 hours is eliminated in the above manner without causing any break through of the gas (35). Since most of the sulphur is fixed by carbon as carbon-sulphur surface complex, the capacity of the carbon for the reaction depends on the concentration of unsaturated sites.

Interaction with nitrogen dioxide also takes place equally efficiently, the optimum temperature being 400° (37). The reaction involves fixation of oxygen at the unsaturated sites.

The reactions with sulphur dioxide and nitrogen dioxide are of interest from the point of view of combating air pollution.

A number of redox reactions, as for example, oxidation of Fe^{+2} to Fe^{+3} ion on passing air through the acidified solution at the room temperature, are also catalysed by carbons associated with unsaturated sites (38). The mechanism involves dissociative chemisorption of oxygen at the unsaturated sites and this lowers the energy of activation for the reaction to a value close to 5 kcal/mole.

Effect of Surface Complexes on Surface Behaviour of Carbons

The effect of chemisorbed oxygen on surface properties such as acidity, polarity, hydrophilicity and selectivity in adsorption from binary solutions has already received adequate attention, as has been discussed elsewhere by the author (1). The recent trends have been to spell out separately the effect of the various oxygen complexes (such as acidic CO_2^- complex, non acidic CO_2^- complex and CO_- complex) on some of surface characteristics of the carbons (13, 39, 40). The work from these laboratories has established that it is the presence of the acidic CO_2^- complex and not the total combined oxygen as such, considered by previous workers, which imparts, acidic, polar and hydrophilic character (12,

13, 41) to the surface. The rest of the combined oxygen has little or no effect on these properties.

A study of selective adsorption by carbons from binary solutions of methanol-benzene, methanol-carbon tetrachloride and ethanol-cyclohexane solutions has shown that the view of previous workers (42, 43) that the combined oxygen as a whole enhances selective adsorption of a more polar component of the mixture cannot be substantiated. Thus, while the presence of acidic CO_2^- complex enhances preference of the surface for methanol, the more polar component of methanol-benzene mixture, that of the non-acidic complex in which the oxygen is believed to be fixed at the unsaturated sites has little or no effect (44). The presence of oxygen that comes off as carbon monoxide (CO_- complex), on the other hand, enhances preference of the surface for benzene, the less polar component of methanol-benzene system. This is attributed to the interaction of π electrons of benzene with the partial positive charge on quinonic oxygen which constitutes a part of the CO_- complex. These observations suggest the desirability of determining the nature of disposition of the combined oxygen and not merely the total oxygen in understanding surface characteristics of carbon blacks.

A study of the effect of surface oxygen complexes on adsorption isotherms of benzene (45) has confirmed that while the presence of the acidic CO_2^- complex imparts polar character to the surface and, therefore, suppresses sorption of benzene, its elimination and the emergence of CO_- complex as the only predominant complex on the surface, enhances the sorption at all relative vapour pressures. The additional sorption amounts roughly to one mole of benzene per quinonic oxygen. The isosteric heat of adsorption of benzene is also higher than the usual value, in the presence of quinonic oxygen. The use of benzene isotherms for estimating pore volume (46) or surface area (47, 48) of carbons, therefore, needs revision in the light of these observations.

The presence of sulphur complexes has been shown to render the carbon surface increasingly hydrophilic besides causing a significant fall in solid-gas interfacial area (49).

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